

A Comparative study on Six Sigma based Modified Quick Switching Systems

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Abstract

This paper compares the two six sigma based quick switching systems (QSS-2 and QSS-3) with parameters (n, kn, c_0) through Mathematical modelling and performance evaluation. The Poisson distribution is used as a fundamental distribution for developing table values. This comparative study investigates and analyses the similarities and differences between modified quick switching systems.

Keywords: *Six Sigma, Quick Switching Systems, Process optimization, Modified QSS*

Introduction

Six sigma approaches have been used in the manufacturing and process optimization field to pursuit of efficiency, enhance flexibility and reduce faults. Quick switching systems play an important role in minimizing changeover time and maximizing production efficiency. This study explains comparative analysis of two specific quick switching systems, namely QSS-2 and QSS-3 with parameters (n, kn, c_0) .

The Quick switching system is ability to rapidly switch between normal and tightened plans was proposed by Dodge(1967) . Ramboski (1969) developed quick switching system, which is known as modified quick switching system. The quick switching system (QSS-2) is a system that examines the normal single sampling plan (n, c_0) and the tightened plan (kn, c_0) where $k > 1$ for the assumed p_1, p_2, α and β .

Six Sigma

Six sigma is a strategy that involves the arrangement of the system and methods to eliminate defects, improves quality and achieve operational excellence. Six sigma means a cycle that works with the limit of 3.4 imperfections per one million opportunities. Six sigma quality level (SSQL)

was presented by Radhakrishnan and Sivakumaran (2008), developed different strategies for developing and selecting different test plans and frameworks using SSQL-1 and SSQL-2. The modified QSS-2(N, C_N, C_T) was developed by Sivakumaran and Kiruthika (2020) by using six sigma quality levels. Mani and Sivakumaran(2020) constructed six sigma based quick switching system (QSS-2) with parameters (n, kn, c_0). Further Mani and Sivakumaran(2021) developed six sigma based modified quick switching system (QSS-3) with parameters (n, kn, c_0).

Conditions for Application

- The Manufacturing process agrees that the result of current and previous batches are generally indicative of the ongoing and that the quality of submitted batches is considered to substantially equivalent.
- The lot must be significant within the production system.
- Testing is performed according to the characteristics and quality is expressed as percentage of defects.
- Required less human involvement in the manufacturing process.

Operating Characteristic function of Modified QSS is given by

The Operating characteristic function for QSS-2 and QSS-3 with parameters (n, kn, c_0) derived by Romboski (1969)

QSS-2(n, kn, c_0) is given by

$$p_a(p) = \frac{A.B^2+B(1-A)(1+B)}{(B^2+(1-A)(1+B))} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

The QSS-3 (n, kn, c_0) OC function is given by

$$P_a(p) = \frac{A.B^4 + r(1-A)(1+B^2)(1+B)}{B^4+(1-A)(1+B)(1+B^2)} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where $A = \sum_{i=0}^{c_0} \frac{e^{-np}(np)^i}{i!}$ and $B = \sum_{j=0}^{c_0} \frac{e^{-knp}(knp)^j}{j!}$

Where,

A= Proportion of lots expected to be accepted when using single sampling Normal plan (n, c_0)

B = Proportion of lots expected to be accepted when using single sampling tightened plan (kn, c_0).

Construction of Modified QSS(n, kn, c_0) using P_{SSQL-1}:

$P_a(p)$ of a lot, given in equations 1 and 2 for QSS-2 and QSS-3 is fixed as 1-3.4 / one million opportunities, considering Poisson distribution as basic distribution. The calculated values of nP_{SSQL-1} are tabulated in table 1 by using Excel program with different ‘ c_0 ’ and ‘ k ’. The sample size ‘ n ’ is got from the relationship $n = nP_{SSQL-1} / P_{SSQL-1}$ and the parameters n, kn and c_0 of QSS-2 and

QSS-3. Process sigma values are calculated for different values of P_{SSQL-1} with the help of the process Sigma Calculator “(<http://www.isixsigma.com/>)”, the sample size and the acceptance number, process sigma levels are computed.

Example 1: The value of nP_{SSQL-1} chosen from the table 1 is 0.0275044 assuming $P_{SSQL-1} = 0.00001$, $c_0 = 2$ and $k = 1$ and the calculated sample size ‘n’ is $n = 0.0275044/0.00001 = 2750$, which corresponds to the sigma level of 4.68. Hence the parameters of QSS-2 are $n = 2750$, $kn=2750$ and $c_0 = 2$ for a specified $P_{SSQL-1} = 0.00001$.

Example 2: The value of nP_{SSQL-1} chosen from the table 1 is 0.025289 assuming $P_{SSQL-1} = 0.00001$, $c_0 = 2$ and $k = 1$ and the calculated sample size ‘n’ is $n = 0.025289/0.00001 = 2529$, which corresponds to the sigma level of 4.66 . Hence the parameters of QSS-3 are $n = 2529$, $kn=2529$ and $c_0 = 2$ for a specified $P_{SSQL-1} = 0.00001$.

The OC curve for Example 1 and Example 2 is given below:

Practical Application for QSS-2 and QSS-3:

In a standard flask manufacturing company if the manufacturer fixes the level of quality $P_{SSQL-1} = 0.00001$ (1 faulty masks out of ten lakh masks). A sample of 2750 flasks are taken from one lot at random in normal level which has ‘f’ faulty masks. If $f \leq 2$, accept the lot, otherwise do not accept the lot and advice the management for improving quality. if the company adopted QSS-2.If that company is using QSS-3, a sample size of 2529 flasks are taken from a lot at normal level which has ‘f’ faulty items. if $f \leq 2$, accept the lots otherwise do not accept the lot and inform the management for improving quality.

Table 1: Represents parameters of Modified QSS (n, kn, c_0) for a given P_{SSQL-1} .

c_0	k	$P_{SSQL-1}(QSS-2)$	$P_{SSQL-1}(QSS-3)$
1	1	0.0026100	0.0016467
1	5	0.0025712	0.0016222
1	8	0.0024516	0.0015468
2	1	0.0275044	0.0252896
2	5	0.0275126	0.0250367
2	8	0.0263818	0.0242498
3	1	0.0966822	0.0954905
3	5	0.0961625	0.0947643
3	8	0.0938594	0.0924945
4	1	0.2158560	0.2116388
4	5	0.2121183	0.2116354
4	8	0.2121217	0.2116154
5	1	0.3801173	0.3793823
5	5	0.3794964	0.3763775
5	8	0.3754828	0.3532843

Conclusion

A quick switching system allows the switching from the normal inspection to the tightened inspection to improving quality and ensuring acceptance. In this paper Quick switching systems 2 and 3 with parameters (n, kn, c_0) has been constructed by using six sigma quality levels. The table values are developed with the assistance of Poisson distribution. This research clearly explains the comparison between QSS-2 and QSS-3, highlighting that QSS-3 is the superior system for reducing sample size and improving operating characteristics. It is illustrated with suitable example. This system proves very useful for companies and management teams to adhering six sigma quality standards.

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